

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS THROUGH THE HEURISTIC METHOD

Israilova N

Teacher of Namangan Branch of Tashkent International University of Chemistry

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364493>

Abstract. *This article discusses the use of a heuristic method for the formation of professional competence of teachers using the heuristic method. In order for the personnel being trained today to occupy a worthy place in the labor market, innovative design of educational content is presented; division of professional competencies into components; creation of new methodological models of education and analysis of scientific sources for their application in specific educational practice.*

Keywords: *teacher, educator, competence, heuristic method, integration, creativity, Caspian competence, non-standard thinking.*

In the process of integration of production and education in the world, development of professional competence of pedagogues-educators, wide use of advanced technology and software tools in higher education, integration of traditional and modern methods of teaching are recognized as one of the urgent tasks [1]. In several prestigious scientific research centers, studies on improving the quality of education are being conducted and significant practical results are being achieved.

Development of creative abilities of students in the educational process, development of the process of innovative preparation for professional activity, improvement of the methodology of using software training tools is gaining importance [2]. Harmonization with the levels of the international standard classification of education (ISCO) adopted by UNESCO, full implementation of the National Qualification System in the educational process, innovative design of the educational content for the qualified personnel to occupy a worthy place in the labor market, division of professional competences into components, creation of new methodological models of education and their special attention is paid to application in specific educational practice.

In this regard Sh.Shodiev, M.Ahmedov, N.Muslimov, V.Abduazizova, M. Kadirova's contribution to the development of methods and forms of development of methods and forms of development of didactic content of creative activity, the scientific features of creative activity, the current issues of development of professional qualities and creative abilities of future pedagogues, as well as the scientific features of creative activity, is a great contribution of Kadirova.

On the development of professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method. A.Aripjanova, G.Ibragimova, G.Kodirova, Sh. Pozilova, F.Sodikova, G.Ibragimova, K.Yusupova, M.Urazova, A.Khalikov researched and developed scientific recommendations.

Scientists of the CIS countries also studied the professional competence of pedagogues-educators with the help of heuristic methods, the specific forms and methods of developing the creative abilities of preschool children. Scientific works of researchers like L.N.Akhmatova, V.D.Eremeeva, T.P.Khrizman, A.L.Sirotyuk, O.A.Safonova, A.V. Svetkov, L.A.Wenger, A.N.Belkova are of great scientific importance.

According to the above opinions, although researches on improving the methodology of developing heuristic competence of future specialists have been conducted in our country and abroad, we can note that the methodology of developing heuristic competence of future educators in preschool education organizations has not been fully researched.

In the process of research carried out by us, based on the features of developing the professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method, the criteria of professional competence, that is, originality, creativity, development, flexibility, were determined. Practical work was carried out to develop the criteria of non-standard thinking, risk-taking, predictability and integrativeness, and the professional training of pedagogues. As a result, the professional competence of pedagogues-educators was improved by the methods and tools used by the heuristic method.

The model of improvement of the methodology of developing the professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method was carried out based on the principles of individualization, humanism, the principle of group and individual educational unity, consciousness and creative activity in education, fundamentality and practical orientation, as a result, the methodology of the professional heuristic method of pedagogues-educators in preschool educational organizations improved[3].

In forming the professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method, the ability to create an interactive-methodical lesson project, creative methods, situational tasks, and the method of applying cognitive-heuristic methods in practice was achieved. As a result, the professional competence of pedagogues-educators was improved by the methods and tools used by the heuristic method.

Development of professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method develops problem situations and creative practical assignments of an interactive-methodical nature[4].

In short, the practical significance of the research is that the development of the professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method was created as a pilot program for improving the development methodology. is determined. Improving the methodology of developing the professional competence of pedagogues-educators through the heuristic method serves to increase the quality of education by creating methodological support for the organization of creative activities in the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Incheon declaration/ Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea). - 68 б.
2. Муслимов Н.А. Бўлажак касб таълими ўқитувчиларини касбий шакллантириш / Монография. – Т.: Фан, 2004.
3. Хамраева, А. Ф. (2021). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАСИ ТАЛАБАЛАРИДА КАСБИЙ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИКНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ТАВФСИФИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(10), 1110-1114.
4. Воронин, В. Н. Интеграция эвристических и технологических подходов проектирования дидактических комплексов в вузе [Текст] / В. Н. Воронин. – Тольятти: Мир, 2003. – 274 с.